

**"THE ROLE OF THE HISTORY OF CARPET
WEAVING IN THE APPLIED ARTS"**

Ahmadaliyeva Jumagul Maqsudali qizi

Student of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726956>

Annotation

This article tells about the art of carpet weaving, the history of development and the process of weaving, the development in neighboring countries and the weaving of different types of carpets

Keywords: Carpets, Carpets, Special Carpets, Carpets

At the beginning of the 20th century, about 50 Uzbek tribes lived in the Samarkand region. One tribe was united and the other was scattered, and they were in constant contact with each other.

According to Grebenkin, at the end of the 19th century, the art of carpet weaving was developed by the following Uzbek tribes: Nayman, Ming, Kutchi, Bagrin, Chinese, Kipchak, Mitan, and Turk.

The Uzbek tribes also included the Karakalpaks. They make woolen rugs and other carpets. Without a detailed description of Uzbek carpet products, A.D. Gerbenkin distinguishes the works of mitan carpet weavers: carpets, rugs, carpets, felt, felt, sacks and others.

He spoke about the carpet weavers of the Turkic and Yuz population of the semi-nomadic Uzbek tribes living around Samarkand and on the borders of the old Khojant. AA Semyonov confirmed and expanded the data of AD Gerbenkin.

Turkish carpet weavers in the Samarkand region write that with the simplest technique, colored rugs are woven into felt and very hard-working Gadjari rugs. M.F.Gavrilov. In his other work, he gave detailed information about the Parchayuz Uzbek tribe, which is very interesting. But Gerbenkin mentioned hundreds of carpet weavers in his report. According to several authors, the oldest tribes in the Uzbek carpet weaving group are of particular interest. (Turks and unguates) as well as the inhabitants of other newly settled districts in Central Asia: the Mitan, who considered the deserts of southeastern Europe as their ancient homeland, came from the eastern districts of the Fergana Valley; The box came from Kashgar. Tribes of various clans were involved in carpet weaving.

All researchers agree that intermarriage between different tribal groups represented a unique culture and tradition. In intermarriage, one tribe is intertwined with another. They presented various carpet works. These rugs use

tribal patterns, which unite the family's loyalty to each other and are later used for household needs.

The gradual introduction of farming and arable farming has led to a significant reduction in carpet weaving. According to statistics and archives, in the late 19th and early 1970s, Uzbek carpet-weaving tribes in Samarkand district accounted for only 25%. During the year, carpet weaving in several villages consisted of 10 carpets and rugs: most of these rugs could be seen in the market.

The process of shrinking carpet production continued until the early twentieth century.

The inspected auls contained only ancient specimens of pat-carpet products. The members of the expedition did not meet a carpet weaver who knew how to weave these rugs and the patterns used in them. Also, the tools used in these rugs have not been preserved. Heavy machinery was no longer produced, but it was still familiar to many women. Most women are aware that palisade patterns are only technically moisturizing. The special names "Seven Strings" and "Four Strings" were almost forgotten. But all the carpet work was the work of the natives. They are made by older women. In the 1920s, only simple road palos and kojims were made. In the villages, women weaved carpets not for sale, but for their own use. However, carpet weavers from Zaamin and Jizzakh also make carpet products for sale. (Zaamin, Ravot, Korpasat, Qayli, Yoyishla)

Special rugs are made - to be worshiped, to be hung on the inside of the doors, to be hung on the top of the door. The floor-to-ceiling materials for the benches, for the chairs, for the yard or for the garden are made of palos, buckets and kokhs and various techniques.

Among the Uzbek tribes, small carpets are produced in a significant variety. The tribe weaves a variety of rugs, carpets, rugs, baskets and other products to attach the furniture and equipment. (picture - 20). They were bought not only by the villagers but also by the townspeople, mainly Russians, for use in various upholstered furniture, pillows and other types of furniture. By the beginning of the twentieth century, their production declined sharply. The ancient patterns of rugs have not survived to the present day, they are of high artistic quality, and the population has made sacks and bags for carpets and things that are not large in size. Unfortunately, this interesting carpet work is poorly understood.

Also included are large sacks of household utensils - napramach. (picture - 21). To make the napramach, as in other bags and sacks, only the surface of the carpet was used, and the other side was made of simple, unadorned, woolen materials

Most of the ancient baskets were made using the palos technique. (Figure 22). Cotton wool was used as an auxiliary tool to sew patterns. In the early twentieth century, cotton began to be used in full for bags.

Bags and sacks are made for economic reasons and are rarely marketed. In the museums of the republic they are presented in the form of very simple napramas.

A carpet is a textile floor covering typically consisting of an upper layer of pile attached to a backing. The pile was traditionally made from wool, but since the 20th century, synthetic fibers such as polypropylene, nylon or polyester are often used, as these fibers are less expensive than wool. The pile usually consists of twisted tufts that are typically heat-treated to maintain their structure. The term carpet is often used in a similar context to the term rug, but rugs are typically considered to be smaller than a room and not attached to the floor.

Carpet weaving is a carpet weaving and artistic craft. It has long been common among nomadic tribes engaged in animal husbandry. Plant fiber (cotton, flax, jute), wool (sheep, goat, camel wool) are made only. For weaving carpets, sheared wool is washed and cleaned, combed with iron combs, and yarn is spun from the combed wool. The threads are dyed with various natural dyes. Therefore, the color of the carpet does not change and does not lose its quality. Nowadays it is also woven from synthetic fibers. G. is woven on horizontal (horizontal) and vertical (vertical) looms. In the G. developed areas, looms have been greatly improved, and a wide variety of spools has been created in which several weavers sit side by side and weave at once. The carpet weaver weaves the sculpture on the basis of iodine or copy. There are different types of rugs and non-rugs depending on the method of weaving.

Hand-woven carpets are widespread in Central Asia, especially in Turkmenistan. Weaving carpets by hand is extremely labor-intensive and requires perseverance, taste and skill from the weaver. Weaving rugs is especially difficult. The hand-woven carpet is made of colored threads on the base thread, the end of the knot is cut flat on the surface of the fabric, and after each row the back thread is passed through a special iron comb and fastened to the previous one. The finished carpet is washed using special chemicals. Carpets are made in different sizes. It was not until the 1930s that special machine-tool enterprises (including the Mehnat Guli artel in Andijan) emerged. Iranian, Turkish, Turkmen and Azerbaijani carpets, which differ in location, pattern, quality (thickness, length of the patina), color scheme, produced in Sharq G., have long been popular.

It is difficult to say the exact time of the appearance of the carpet, because the wool is unstable. Carpets are not stored. The tallest carpet mil. av. It dates back to the 6th-5th centuries, was found in the Altai Mountains, and is well preserved because it is in permafrost. Scholars have suggested that it was made by the Achaemenid Persians or Central Asian tribes (1.8 x 2 m; sculpture: hand-shaped figures decorated with lily flowers, with wide borders depicting horsemen, spotted deer, and griffins).

Qad. and information on early medieval carpet weaving is preserved in written sources. During the Seljuk period, carpets ("konya", after the place where they were found) were made in large numbers and exported to Egypt, India, and China.

In the Middle Ages, carpet weaving developed in three directions - in nomadic and semi-nomadic pastoral tribes, among the settled (rural or urban) population, and in palace workshops. Researchers have singled out Iranian, Transcaucasian, and Central Asian carpets.

Palace (Iranian) carpets have been well preserved since the 16th century. These carpets ("Orange", "Shah Abbas", "Garden", "Hunting", etc.) are rare examples of applied art. They are based on the drawings of miniature artists. G. Turkey developed during the Baburid period in India ("Mongol", "Agra" and other carpets), behind Egypt, Syria and the Caucasus.

In the 18th and 19th centuries, G. was widespread in the Caucasus and Central Asia, not in palaces, but among the people. Transcaucasian carpets, the main centers of which are Kazakhstan, Ganja, Shirvan, Baku, Nakhichevan. It is characterized by depth, handasia flowers and extreme firmness.

In Western Europe, Flemish, French, and German trellis have had a special place since the 16th century. From the 17th to the 18th century, rugs began to be made (in the Savoneri manufactory, founded in Paris in 1624), and later rugs were made in England and Spain. From the 19th century onwards, when carpets began to be produced in factories, its quality declined sharply. Attempts to recreate G. in the arts and crafts since the mid-20th century have been successful. Along with Polish, Bulgarian, Romanian, and Yugoslav rugs, rugless rugs were also produced.

Carpet weaving has been developed since ancient times in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan (during archeological excavations in Khorezm, a carpet pattern dating back to the 1st millennium BC was found). G. was mainly practiced by women, and memorized patterns (flowers) (Islamic, girih, animal forms, images of various objects, seed marks, etc.). The ornaments depict tiger

and camel prints, apple blossoms, grape bells, camel necks, shields, and plants, especially animal horns. The solidity of the sculpture, the central square surrounded by a patterned border (with the exception of striped patterns) are typical of Central Asian carpets, and the precision, beauty, and harmony of the colors add to their artistic value. The main color is red and its 2-3 camels, while blue, black, white and yellow are secondary. An expressive image is created with the skillful use of colors. Variety and attractiveness are achieved by painting the parts of a pattern in different ways.

Andijan and Samarkand carpets and Karakalpak grass were skillfully crafted. Andijan carpets were short, thick and soft. Samarkand's colorful long-haired julkhirs ("bear skin") rug is unique.

By the 20th century, carpet weaving had developed in a unique way, carpet weaving was developed in the centers of G., artels were formed and folk artisans were involved (eg, carpet weaving artel in Oyim village, Andijan region). , small household items were woven. From the second half of the 1930s, there were attempts to create themed and pictorial rugs. In the centers of G. Caucasian carpets, somewhat simplified carpets in the form of traditional Turkmen carpets were produced, only Samarkand carpets (julkhirs) retained their traditional style and color. In the 1940s and 1950s, G. Centers (Samarkand, Kitab, 1946; Khiva, Andijan, Termez, 1947; Shakhrisabz, 1949; Khojayli, 1954) were established, local masters trained students, traditional patterns have been restored. Success was achieved as a result of the collaboration of artists and craftsmen. Using the traditions of applied and majestic art, the first new copy of the Khorezm carpet and its unique turquoise floor were created.

In the late 1960s, small artels were merged to form new G. enterprises, and skilled craftsmen began to work in these enterprises. Almalyk, Samarkand, Khiva, Forish, Shafirkan and others. Local factories produce traditional carpets and elegantly enriched carpets.

Использованная литература:

1. Ortiqboy, S. S., & Makhsudali, J. (2022). A Desire Sung in a Pattern. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN, 3(5), 6-9.
2. Prozorova, M. N., Zharkov, A. D., Zharkova, A. A., Khamdamova, V. A., Sattorova, S. O., & Losev, V. S. (2021). University graduate career potential in digital transformation period: Features and problems of formation. Linguistics and Culture Review, 5(S3), 1574-1585.
3. Sattorova, S. O. (2021). PATTERN SUNG ON THE CARPET. Экономика и социум, (5-1), 445-448.

4. Abdurahimovich, M. A., & Qizi, S. S. O. (2020). Master Student Etiquette. www.conferencepublication.com, 22.
5. Khaydarovich, A. A. (2020). Colors in Descriptive Art. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 2(12), 20-22.
6. Mamadjananivich, B. B. IT is Necessary to Feed the World with Beauty!. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(8), 215-217.
7. Sarvinoz Sattorova Ortiqboy qizi "Экономика и социум" Страницы 445-448, №5(84) 2021 www.iupr.ru
8. "Definition of carpet". Thefreedictionary.com. Retrieved 2013-10-04.
9. "Carpet - Definition". Merriam-webster.com. 2012-08-31. Retrieved 2013-10-04.
10. Jump up to: a b c d e f g "carpet - Search Online Etymology Dictionary". www.etymonline.com.

